

A Study of the Nature of Slope, S_v , of ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{C}$ Curves for some Tetra-alkylammonium Salts in NMA – DMSO Solvent Mixture. Part-I

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A study of the nature of slope S_v in plots of apparent molal volume vs $\sqrt{\text{concentration}}$ for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI salts in NMA – DMSO solvent mixtures of varying dielectric constant has been carried out in both lower (0.002 – 0.012 M) and higher (0.02 – 0.12 M) concentration ranges using magnetic float densitometer. Et_4NI shows positive slope in dilute as well as in concentrated solutions, Pr_4NI does so only in concentrated solutions while in dilute range slope changes from positive to negative. Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI salts indicate a transition in slope in both the ranges of concentration..

FROM a large number of studies on Masson's equation it appears that in general for R_4NX salts, a negative slope occurs only in solvents of high dielectric constant. Common salts generally show +ve slope in media having both low and high dielectric constant except for few exceptions comprising NaBr, NaNO_3 and NH_4Br in NMP^{1,2} and NaCl, NaBr, KBr and KNO_3 in NMA³ which indicate –ve slope. In an attempt to get a clear picture of the behaviour of the slope, a few aqueous-nonaqueous solvent mixtures, e.g. dioxane – water⁴, methanol – water⁵, ethanol – water⁶, t-butyl alcohol – water⁷, NMA – water⁸ and NMP – water⁹ were studied by different workers. The results appear to indicate strong dependence of the nature of the slope on dielectric constant.

These studies on the solvent mixtures having components of two different nature, one being an aqueous and the other non-aqueous, may have some effect on the nature of the slope due to the presence of one in the other. So it seemed worthwhile to extend our studies to solvent mixtures having both the components and having varying dielectric constant. The present study is on R_4NX salts in mixtures of *N*-methylacetamide and dimethyl sulphoxide. The components of this mixture were such that the magnetic float densitometer, described in detail elsewhere¹⁰, may be able to record the density, since our apparatus design is such that it can measure the density values which are not less than 0.9889 g ml⁻¹, the density of the float.

Furthermore, to investigate the problem of the slope more critically and accurately both low concentration and high concentration ranges of the electrolytes have been examined. The low dielectric constant value of DMSO has been increased by adding NMA to DMSO to obtain mixtures of varying dielectric constant. Four mixtures having com-

positions 0, 20, 40 and 60% NMA in DMSO (v/v) are taken. The dielectric constants of such mixtures not being known, have been worked out assuming a linear relationship between the dielectric constant and percentage composition.

Experimental

N-Methylacetamide (Fluka, purum) was fractionally crystallised and kept overnight on freshly ignited quicklime. It was then distilled under reduced pressure and the middle fraction was collected. The above process was repeated with the middle fraction till the electrical conductance of the sample was of the order of $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1}$ or less. The second solvent dimethyl sulphoxide (Fluka, purum) was purified by first refluxing it for several hours with freshly ignited quicklime and then distilling under reduced pressure. The middle fractions of the successive distillate were redistilled under reduced pressure till the electrical conductance of the final product was $\leq 10^{-7} \Omega^{-1}$. The purified samples were stored in dark-coloured bottles and kept in a dry-box until used. The tetra-alkylammonium iodides were purified by usual manner¹¹, dried and kept in a vacuum desiccator.

Four compositions of the solvent mixtures of 0 ($\epsilon_{25^\circ} = 46.6$), 20 (72.6), 40 (99.0) and 60% NMA (125.6) in DMSO (v/v) were prepared. The solutions of Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI were prepared on molal basis. Two concentration ranges of each electrolyte, one being lower (0.002 – 0.012 M) and the other higher (0.02 – 0.12 M), were used in the present study. The densities of these solutions were measured by the magnetic float densitometer as described elsewhere¹⁰. The whole apparatus was immersed in a Toshniwal constant temperature bath at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$. The following procedure was

TABLE 1—TETRAETHYLAMMONIUM IODIDE
0% NMA in DMSO, $d_0 = 1.101\ 232\ \text{g ml}^{-1}$

Sl. no.	M	w g	i mA	d g ml ⁻¹	$\sqrt{c}$ (c =molarity)	ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹
Low concentration :						
1.	0.002	9.950	176	1.101 399	0.047	164.25
2.	0.004	9.000	156	1.101 566	0.066	164.65
3.	0.006	9.050	185	1.101 730	0.081	164.80
4.	0.008	9.100	115	1.101 895	0.094	165.05
5.	0.010	9.150	95	1.102 060	0.105	165.10
6.	0.012	9.200	75	1.102 220	0.115	165.40
High concentration :						
1.	0.02	9.300	45	1.102 788	0.148	169.10
2.	0.04	9.350	87	1.104 297	0.209	169.85
3.	0.06	9.600	17	1.105 788	0.255	170.50
4.	0.08	9.700	28	1.107 230	0.294	170.75
5.	0.10	9.800	37	1.108 640	0.328	171.30
6.	0.12	9.900	49	1.110 090	0.358	171.55

adopted to find out the densities of various solutions by this instrument. The magnetic float densitometer was first calibrated with distilled water at 25° in the manner described earlier¹⁰. The weight equivalent (f) was found out to be 1.71 g A⁻¹ and the volume (V) of the float 78.28 cm³. The weight of the float came out to be 77.4240 g.

The solution, whose density was to be determined, was taken in the solution container. Then the maximum possible weights of Pt were put on the float, floating inside the solution container, so that further increase in weights would make the float to sink in the solution. Now the current in the pulldown solenoid was passed to bring the float down inside the solution. Then the main solenoid circuit was put in operation. The amount of current in the circuit was regulated by the resistance bridge used therein. The value of the current was found out so that the platinum point of the float first touched the bottom and then after a little adjustment in current it just left the surface. This critical value of the current was read in terms of millivolt across 1 Ω standard resistor. For each solution the weights and the corresponding current were measured. The density of the solution was calculated by using the equation¹⁰,

$$d_{\text{soln}}^{\text{25}} = \frac{W + w + f_i}{V_{\text{25}} + \frac{w}{d_{\text{Pt}}^{\text{25}}}}$$

The densities of Et₄Ni, Pr₄Ni, Bu₄Ni and Pen₄Ni solutions of different concentrations in various solvent mixtures of NMA in DMSO were calculated. From densities ϕ_v values were calculated in usual manner⁸. Data for one of such solutions are given in Table 1. ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{c}$ plots are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

Earlier, dilatometric technique of finding the densities of solutions was employed in this labora-

tory. The method did not allow one to measure the densities of very dilute solutions accurately. Magnetic float densitometer¹⁰ however enables one to measure the densities of very dilute as well as very concentrated solutions accurately upto sixth place of decimal.

It has been seen experimentally that for the same solution, if the weight is increased corresponding current will decrease and vice versa. But for different solutions there may not be regularity in weights and corresponding values of current. The values of the density of each of the pure solvent mixtures (d_0) have also been calculated and one such value has been given at the top of Table 1¹². For 0, 20, 40 and 60% NMA in DMSO, the d_0 values are 1.101 232, 1.072 629, 1.043 426 and 1.014 623

Fig. 1. ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{c}$ curves for Et₄Ni in NMA + DMSO mixtures at 25°; concn. range = 0.002 - 0.012 M.

Fig. 2. ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{c}$ curves for Et_4NI in NMA + DMSO mixtures at 25° ; concn. range = 0.02–0.12 M.

g ml⁻¹ respectively. Me_4NI could not be examined in these mixtures due to solubility restrictions.

It is evident from Figs. 1 and 2 that ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{c}$ curves, for all the four electrolytes, viz. Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in both the concentration ranges (lower and higher) and in all the mixtures, are straight lines indicating that Masson's equation applies in all the cases. If individual electrolyte is examined then it is found that for a particular concentration in each case the apparent molal volume increases with increase in the dielectric constant of the medium. The slope S_v in ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{c}$ curves is positive for Et_4NI whether the solution is dilute or concentrated. But in case of Pr_4NI , it is very interesting to note that dilute solutions first give +ve slope and as the dielectric constant of the medium is increased, the slope becomes -ve; concentrated solutions of Pr_4NI , however, indicate +ve slope in all the solvent mixtures. Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI salts give +ve slope in both the regions of concentration, in lower dielectric constant media and the slope becomes negative as the dielectric constant of the medium is raised. The effect of variation of the dielectric constant can be seen more explicitly when S_v values are plotted against dielectric constant. The results are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. From Table 1 and these graphs it is evident that all the four electrolytes show the common feature of decreasing slope with increase in dielectric constant of the medium. In some cases it even becomes -ve. For dilute solutions Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI give respectively 62, 59.2 and 52 as the critical value of the dielectric constants, 'the transition points'. Below this the slope is always positive and above this it is negative. If concentrated solutions of these electrolytes are considered then Pr_4NI behaves in somewhat different manner. It does not give negative slope while the other two salts Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI do, and the critical value of the dielectric

Fig. 3. S_v vs ϵ curves for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in NMA–DMSO mixtures at 25° ; concn. range = 0.002–0.012 M.

Fig. 4. S_v vs ϵ curves for Et_4NI , Pr_4NI , Bu_4NI and Pen_4NI in NMA–DMSO mixtures at 25° ; concn. range = 0.02–0.12 M.

constant (ϵ) comes out to be 62 for Bu_4NI and 49.6 for Pen_4NI . From the above discussion the conclusion is drawn that the dielectric constant of the medium appears to strongly affect the S_v values or in other words, it plays an important role in determining the nature of the slope in ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{c}$ curve.

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